

The Innovative Role of Entrepreneurship Courses in Shaping The Entrepreneurial Mindset of Generation Z: A Systematic Literature Review

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received November 05, 2025

Revised 10 November 2025

Accepted 15 November 2025

Available online 20 November 2025

Keywords

Business education, Generation Z, entrepreneurial attitude, experiential learning, and educational innovation.

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to analyze innovative business practices in fostering an entrepreneurial mindset among Generation Z thru a Systematic Literature Review (SLR). 16 scholarly articles from Google Scholar published between 2020 and 2025 are examined. The literature selection process adheres to the PRISMA guidelines, which encompass the study question, literature review, inclusion and exclusion criteria, quality assessment (QA1–QA3), data collection, and results. The analysis results show that college entrepreneurship has a significant impact on the development of Generation Z students' entrepreneurial mindset thru project-based learning and experiential learning. The type of educational innovation that has the greatest impact on the development of Generation Z businesses includes industry collaboration, mentorship practices, and the integration of digital technology into the learning process. In addition, the success of entrepreneurship education for Generation Z is greatly influenced by collaborative campus environments, access to business incubators, and the use of digital platforms as concept exploration media. The results of this study indicate that the development of the Entrepreneurship course must be based on an application-based,

technologically adaptive, and real-world-oriented learning paradigm in order to foster an entrepreneurial attitude.

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship has become extremely important for the economic and social progress of a nation in the era of disruption and increasing digital technology. As the world's economic system changes, one must have the ability to adapt, be creative, and innovative. Therefore, higher education is crucial for creating a workforce-ready and entrepreneurial generation (Perera & Samarasinghe, 2023). This aligns with the national education goal of producing independent and globally competitive human resources (Tan et al., 2023).

Higher education institutions must change to provide graduates who are employable and create jobs due to the changing social, economic, and technological landscape of the 21st century. In this regard, entrepreneurship courses become an important part of the higher education curriculum because they help students acquire an innovative, creative, and adaptive entrepreneurial mindset (Tan et al., 2023). Entrepreneurship education in higher education is no longer limited to creating business plans; the focus now is on building an entrepreneurial mindset and actions thru challenging and practice-based learning experiences (Saputra & Fahlia, 2022).

Currently, Generation Z, born roughly between the mid-1990s and early 2010s, dominates college campuses. This generation is unique because they are familiar with digital technology, accustomed to working quickly, more independent, and prefer flexible and interactive learning (Sudaryanto & Sylvana, 2023). Generation Z strongly favors innovation and independence in entrepreneurship, but they often face challenges in managing risk, consistency, and entrepreneurial resilience (Sudaryanto & Sylvana, 2023). This indicates that the conventional approach to entrepreneurship education is no longer suitable for the characteristics of

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Generation Z. Studies show that entrepreneurial mindset and digital literacy have a significant influence on Gen Z's decision to become college students (Saputra & Fahlia, 2022). Additionally, it has been shown that entrepreneurial attitudes and self-efficacy serve as important mediators between entrepreneurship education and students' entrepreneurial intentions (Tan et al., 2023). Conversely, global research found that Gen Z's entrepreneurial tendencies are influenced by their learning environment and personality. Therefore, contextual and innovative learning is key to the success of entrepreneurship education (Perera & Samarasinghe, 2023).

Unfortunately, most previous research still focuses on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention, rather than on innovation in the learning process. In fact, developing an entrepreneurial mindset requires a creative pedagogical approach—such as experiential learning, collaboration with industry, and the use of digital technology (Tan et al., 2023; Wijaya et al., 2024). This gap highlights the need for a systematic literature review that comprehensively explores how innovative entrepreneurship courses can play a role in shaping the entrepreneurial mindset of Generation Z students in higher education.

Therefore, it is hoped that this research can provide a conceptual and empirical mapping of the most successful innovative learning models. Additionally, this research will provide suggestions for developing an entrepreneurship curriculum and teaching strategies that are suitable for the characteristics of Generation Z.

RESEARCH METHOD

A Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach was used in this study to comprehensively review the innovative role of entrepreneurship courses in building the entrepreneurial mindset of Generation Z at universities. This method was chosen because it has the ability to provide a comprehensive overview of previous research findings, identify differences in research, and establish a path toward the advancement of evidence-based entrepreneurship learning (Kitchenham & Charters, 2007; Snyder, 2019). The stages in this SLR use six steps: research question, literature search, inclusion and exclusion methods, quality assessment, data collection, and reporting (Resnawita & Hendrik, 2023).

Research Question

To assist in the literature search and analysis process, the main research question is:

RQ1: How is the entrepreneurship course in a growth mindset for Generation Z entrepreneurs in higher education?

RQ2: What type of learning innovation is most influential on the business thinking of Generation Z?

RQ3: With what assistance are Gen Z students able to learn innovative entrepreneurship?

The PICO (Population, Intervention, Context, and Outcome) approach was used to construct this question. In this approach, the population is Generation Z students, the intervention is inventive entrepreneurship learning, the context is higher education institutions, and the outcome is entrepreneurial outlook (Booth et al., 2016).

Literature Search

The literature search phase was conducted systematically using several academic databases such as Google Scholar. The keywords used in Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.com/>) were: ("entrepreneurship course" OR "entrepreneurship course") AND ("Generation Z" OR "Gen Z") AND ("entrepreneurial mindset" OR "entrepreneurial intention") AND ("experiential learning" OR "project-based"). Recent developments in Generation Z entrepreneurship education in the digital and post-pandemic era are driving the search process for the 2020–2025 period.

Inclusion and Exclusion Methods

The next step is the feasibility testing process. The articles discussed in the article were selected thru a rigorous process, and each article was identified. The inclusion and exclusion criteria in this article are as follows: Inclusion Criteria: a. Scientific research articles published on Google Scholar. b. Scientific article publications between 2020 and 2025. c. The discussion focuses on entrepreneurship education in higher education. d. Generation Z, born between 1996 and 2010, is the research subject. e. The article discusses business mindset or learning innovation. f. Research journals that are fully accessible. Exclusion Criteria: a. Articles discussing high school or vocational school students. b. Research that ignores innovation in learning. c. The article may be a replica or not available in its full version.

Quality Assessment

The eligibility and credibility of each product that passes the inclusion stage are evaluated thru a quality assessment (QA) process.

QA1: Is the research objective clear, and are the methods and design used appropriate for achieving it?

QA2: Are the data collection procedures and analysis methods reported in sufficient detail and followed in a valid/reliable manner?

QA3: Are the results presented openly (findings, effect sizes if any), are their limitations discussed, and are they relevant to the SLR context (entrepreneurship and Gen Z)?

The answers to each question above will be assessed based on the selected journal: a. Y (yes) indicates a journal that meets the assessment criteria; b. T (no) indicates a journal that does not meet the assessment criteria.

Data Collection

Data was collected after all articles met the inclusion criteria and passed the quality assessment stage. To ensure the synthesis can be conducted systematically and purposefully, the collected data is categorized into three categories: primary data, secondary data, and analysis data (Snyder, 2019; Booth et al., 2016).

1. Primary Data

The primary data for this study came from data extracted from a number of articles relevant to the research topic. Primary data was obtained thru direct digital observation of the original source, Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.com/>). The observation was conducted by thoroughly reviewing articles that met the inclusion criteria. The analysis is tailored to the needs of a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) article.

2. Secondary Data

Secondary data is used to support the interpretation of primary data results. This includes: 1. Books or conceptual articles related to entrepreneurship education and the characteristics of Generation Z. 2. Analysis based on theories such as Entrepreneurial Mindset, Theory of Experiential Learning, and Theory of Planned Behavior. In the results analysis phase, secondary data helps strengthen the context and support interpretive arguments.

3. Data Analysis

Data analysis was collected thru the process of thematic synthesis, or thematic synthesis, of all primary and secondary data. This is done in several stages, for example: a. Initial coding, marking the most important keywords, variables, and themes for each article. b. Grouping topics into four categories: a) Innovation in entrepreneurship learning, b) Developing Generation Z's business perspective, c) Factors supporting and hindering

creative learning, d) Establishing patterns of relationships between themes to answer the main research questions, known as narrative synthesis.

To find consistency, differences, and the direction of entrepreneurship research development in the context of Generation Z students, the analysis was conducted descriptively and interpretatively using a cross-disciplinary literature comparison approach (Snyder, 2019).

Reporting

In the final stage, reporting involves the preparation of a comprehensive research report. The research findings are based on the results and are accompanied by practical suggestions for the future development of Generation Z entrepreneurship research. This research is expected to be published in a journal or conference to contribute to the advancement of knowledge in the field of education.

RESULTS

a. Research Question

Results Relevant and focused research questions are the first step in this study. The main question raised based on the analysis of research problems and weaknesses is "What is the innovative role of entrepreneurship courses in shaping the entrepreneurial mindset of Generation Z at universities?". Two sub-questions were created to deepen the research: (1) what types of learning innovation are used in entrepreneurship courses, and (2) what factors support or hinder the formation of the entrepreneurial mindset of Generation Z.

b. Literature Search

Results The literature search stage was conducted on two main sources, namely Google Scholar. The keywords used in Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.com/>). "entrepreneurship course" OR "entrepreneurial mindset" "Generation Z" OR "Gen Z" "entrepreneurial intention" OR "experiential learning" OR "project-based". During the literature search process, 90 journals from Google Scholar were found that were relevant to the research topic. Next, the articles will be evaluated based on inclusion and exclusion standards

c. Results of Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria Number of Articles :

No	Inclusion Criteria	Number of Articles
1	Scientific journals published in Google Scholar	90 articles
2	Publication of scientific articles between 2020 and 2025	90 articles
3	Scientific research journals that are fully accessible.	53 articles
4	Articles mentioning Generation Z, born between 1996 and 2010, as research subjects.	16 articles
5	The discussion focus relevant to this article is on innovation in entrepreneurship education and the entrepreneurial mindset of Gen Z students.	16 articles

After being examined using inclusion and exclusion criteria, 16 articles were found to meet the criteria. Exclusion criteria include service journals, SLR, research subjects who are not

students, digital books, and many studies that do not focus on the discussion material in this article.

d. Quality Assessment Stages

No.	Title of Scientific Article	QA1	QA2	QA3
1	Growing The Spirit Of Gen Z Entrepreneurial Students In 5.0 Society Era	Y	Y	Y
2	The Role Of Entrepreneurial Motivation As A Mediator For The Campus Environment And Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy In Generation Z	Y	Y	Y
3	Generation Z And Entrepreneurship: Revealing Factors That Affect The Entrepreneurial Intentions	Y	Y	Y
4	Exploring The Influence Of Entrepreneurial Education And Environment On Entrepreneurial Readiness: The Mediating Effects Of Entrepreneurial Mindset And Financial Literacy In Shaping Student Intentions	Y	Y	Y
5	A Problem-Based Learning (PBL) Approach In Effective Implementation Of Innovation And Entrepreneurship Education For Engineering	Y	Y	Y
6	The Effect Of Entrepreneurial Education On University Student's Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy And Entrepreneurial Intention	Y	Y	Y
7	Impact Of Creativity On Students' Entrepreneurial Intention: Study Case On Jakarta	Y	Y	Y
8	Module Validity (M-BMC) Project Based Learning Methods For The Topic Of Business Model Canvas.	Y	Y	Y
9	Does Entrepreneurial Training Change Minds? A Case Study Among Southeast Asian Business Students. Irish Educational	Y	Y	Y
10	Analysis Of The Impact Of Mandatory Entrepreneurship Courses. Entrepreneurship Education And Pedagogy	Y	Y	Y
11	Predicting Entrepreneurial Intentions Through Entrepreneurial Education And The Mediating Role Of Self-Efficacy, Using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM)	Y	Y	Y
12	Peran Paparan Konten Media Sosial Bermuatan Kewirausahaan Dan Penggunaan Tools Digital Marketing Terhadap Kesiapan Wirausaha Dan Keterampilan Digital Marketing Mahasiswa	Y	Y	Y

13	Improving Business Independence of College Students' Generation-Z Through Behavior Entrepreneurship During Pandemic Covid-19	Y	Y	Y
14	Beyond The Classroom: How Entrepreneurial Education And Creativity Drive Student Entrepreneurial Interest Through Motivation At Mulawarman University.	Y	Y	Y
15	Entrepreneurial orientation and entrepreneurial intention: When more learning exposures are efficacious	Y	Y	Y
16	Determinants of Entrepreneurial Intentions Among Polytechnic Students: Evidence from Indonesia	Y	Y	Y

DISCUSSION

There are 3 research questions (RQ1, RQ2, and RQ3) that are clarified and discussed in this section.

RQ1: The Role of Entrepreneurship Courses in Fostering an Entrepreneurial Mindset in Generation Z

Key Findings (synthesis)

- 1) Experiential learning, also known as project-based learning, has consistently been the primary mechanism driving perspective shifts. According to case studies and module evaluations, student involvement in real-world projects, simulations, and incubations provides them with small successes that boost their confidence and focus on opportunities.
- 2) Value-based and contextual content learning, such as local case studies or assignments focused on social or ethical issues, helps students connect their entrepreneurial motivation with their goals. This helps them shift their perspective from simply "knowing" to "understanding" entrepreneurial actions.
- 3) Financial-practical strengthening and market validation, such as pitch competitions and investor mentoring, accelerate attitude change. Students who received market validation reported that their belief that their venture was worth testing had changed, which supported the development of an entrepreneurial mindset.

Supporting Evidence Based on Found Articles

- 1) Research on project-based learning and M-BMC (Module Validity M-BMC) shows how structured business design tasks improve problem-solving skills and the courage to try new things.
- 2) Research on mandatory entrepreneurship courses indicates that entrepreneurial orientation is better when accompanied by practical activities, not just theoretical lectures.

Pedagogical Implications

- 1) In the design of business learning modules, it is necessary to emphasize the experiential cycle. That experience will be a reflection and lead to experimentation (ELT/Kolb).
- 2) Assessment should measure both the process (reflective learning, product literacy) and the final outcome (business plan).

Limitations of Findings

- 1) Many studies were conducted in specific contexts (one university or program), so transferability to other contexts needs to be considered.

2) The amount of standardized quantitative evidence, also known as effect sizes, is still limited to 16 articles. These articles primarily present quantitative descriptive findings or mediation models.

RQ2: The most influential type of learning innovation on Generation Z's business thinking.

Key Findings (the priority in this article is the type of innovation)

Based on the frequency and consistency of results across the 16 articles found:

- 1) Experiential/Project-Based Learning: Real projects, local case studies, and mini-incubations facilitate reflection and practice-based learning.
- 2) Industry Collaboration & Practitioner Mentoring: Learning provided by industry practitioners, start-up mentors, or investors offers real-world market context and networking opportunities.
- 3) Digital-Enhanced Learning (simulations, platforms, and social media tools) facilitates idea validation, rapid prototyping, and virtual market access. This is very effective when combined with real-world experience.
- 4) The Innovation Module/Assessment (micro-credential, iterative assessment, and BMC-based modules) offers a simple, focused learning structure that aligns with Gen Z preferences.

Practical implications for course design

- 1) Prioritize modules that combine project-based assignments with industry mentors and market validation stages (MVP/minimum viable product).
- 2) To accelerate literacy and documentation (portfolios, video pitches), use technology, but still gain field experience.

Limitations.

The effectiveness of each innovation can be influenced by institutional culture, resource support, and faculty readiness. However, these elements were not thoroughly discussed in the 16 scientific research articles found.

RQ3: Supporting Factors for Gen Z Students in Learning Innovative Entrepreneurship

Key Findings (focusing on supporting factors for innovative learning)

Analysis of 16 scientific research articles revealed several important driving factors:

- 1) Mentoring and practitioner role models: Guidance from academic mentors or real entrepreneurs increases motivation, provides practical advice, and builds networks.
- 2) Access to the ecosystem (incubators, competitions, and industry networks): Incubation facilities and competitions provide people with the opportunity to validate ideas, obtain initial funding, and gain experience in running a business.
- 3) Digital facilities and prototyping platforms: Digital tools for prototyping, market testing, and marketing (including digital marketing tools that are taught) help tech-savvy Gen Z quickly test business hypotheses.
- 4) Structured yet flexible curriculum (micro-credentials, tiered modules): short, results-oriented modules align with Gen Z's preference for learning on demand.
- 5) Peer Collaboration & Learning Communities: Peer feedback and campus startup communities reinforce pro-entrepreneurial social norms as Gen Z learns innovative entrepreneurship.

Combination Role (synergy)

- 1) The results show that the combination of mentoring, ecosystem, and experiential tasks is most effective. Mentoring guides practice, the ecosystem provides validation, and experiential tasks nurture the mind.
- 2) Digital tools accelerate this process, but they do not replace the need for mentors and access to the real market.

Limitations

- 1) Many studies report short-term results; evidence regarding sustainability (whether the mindset persists and transforms into entrepreneurial behavior) is still limited.
- 2) Contextual variations (polytechnics vs research universities, different countries) should be considered when generalizing recommendations.

CONCLUSION

From the 16 articles analyzed, it is concluded that entrepreneurship courses play a significant role in shaping the entrepreneurial mindset of Gen Z students, especially when using experiential learning, project-based learning, and digital integration approaches. Practical, contextual, and real-world experience-oriented learning processes have been proven to foster students' self-confidence, creativity, and adaptability to the dynamics of modern business. Additionally, the presence of mentors, ecosystem support, and digital learning serve as reinforcing factors that ensure Gen Z can learn entrepreneurship innovatively and sustainably.

SUGGESTIONS

Most of the studies analyzed still focus on the local context with descriptive or correlational approaches, so further research needs to develop a longitudinal design to track changes in students' mindsets after starting entrepreneurship courses, based on the results of this systematic review. Additionally, experimental learning models are needed to test the effectiveness of various innovations, such as experiential learning, design thinking, and digital incubation. This is necessary to determine the type of method that is most influential on the growth of Generation Z's entrepreneurial mindset.

REFERENCES

- Albornoz, C. A., & Mundaca, C. (2024). Analysis Of The Impact Of Mandatory Entrepreneurship Courses. *Entrepreneurship Education And Pedagogy*, 25151274251337753.
- Alek, M. R. (2025). Determinants Of Entrepreneurial Intentions Among Polytechnic Students: Evidence From Indonesia. *Journal Of Supply Chain And Entrepreneurship*, 1(1), 37-44.
- Anggraeny, C. R. (2023). Impact Of Creativity On Students' Entrepreneurial Intention: Study Case On Jakarta. *Journal Of Business, Management, And Social Studies*, 3(2), 79-93.
- Atmono, D., Rahmattullah, M., Setiawan, A., Mustofa, R. H., Pramudita, D. A., Ulfatun, T., ... & Mustofa, A. (2023). The Effect Of Entrepreneurial Education On University Student's Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy And Entrepreneurial Intention. *International Journal Of Evaluation And Research In Education*, 12(1), 495-504.
- Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2018). *Qualitative Inquiry & Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches* (4th Ed.). Sage Publications.
- Dodoo, P. D., & Yawson, D. E. (2024). Towards An Understanding Of Multi-Generational Higher Education Cohorts In Gamified Entrepreneurship Education. *Heliyon*, 10(11).
- Ei, S., & Sei, M. (2023). Growing The Spirit Of Gen Z Entrepreneurial Students In 5.0 Society Era. Prof. Dr. Deddy Mulyana, 89.
- Hasmidyani, D., Mardetini, E., & Amrina, D. E. (2022). Generation Z And Entrepreneurship: Revealing Factors That Affect The Entrepreneurial Intentions. *Calitatea*, 23(190), 11-19.
- Herijanto, B. A., & Sitepu, S. B. (2025). The Role Of Entrepreneurial Motivation As A Mediator For The Campus Environment And Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy In Generation Z. *Indonesian Journal Of Business And Entrepreneurship*, 11(3), 660-660.
- Kabilan, S. J. (2024). A Problem-Based Learning (Pbl) Approach In Effective Implementation Of

- Innovation And Entrepreneurship Education For Engineering Undergraduates. *Journal Of Engineering Education Transformations*, 120-126.
- Koraag, S. T. G., Zaki, A., Rahmawati, S. A., & Oktafiani, B. (2025). Exploring The Influence Of Entrepreneurial Education And Environment On Entrepreneurial Readiness: The Mediating Effects Of Entrepreneurial Mindset And Financial Literacy In Shaping Student Intentions. *Jurnal Ekonomi Bisnis Dan Kewirausahaan (Jebik)*, 14(1), 1-24.
- Lahouari, S. (2023). Predicting Entrepreneurial Intentions Through Entrepreneurial Education And The Mediating Role Of Self-Efficacy, Using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Model (Pls-Sem). *International Journal Of Economic Performance*, 6(2), 217-235.
- Lahouari, S. (2023). Predicting Entrepreneurial Intentions Through Entrepreneurial Education And The Mediating Role Of Self-Efficacy, Using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Model (Pls-Sem). *International Journal Of Economic Performance*, 6(2), 217-235.
- Le, T. M. H., Hoang, H., & Nguyen, S. T. (2024). Does Entrepreneurial Training Change Minds? A Case Study Among Southeast Asian Business Students. *Irish Educational Studies*, 43(4), 1121-1139.
- Manik, H. F. G. G., & Kusuma, A. S. (2021). Entrepreneurial Orientation And Entrepreneurial Intention: When More Learning Exposures Are Efficacious. *Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis*, 24(2), 271-288.
- Meilani, Y. F. C. P. (2022). Improving Business Independence Of College Students'generation-Z Through Behavior Entrepreneurship During Pandemic Covid-19.
- Nasri, A. K., Che'rus, R., & Syuhaiza, N. Module Validity (M-Bmc) Project Based Learning Methods For The Topic Of Business Model Canvas.
- Sanistasya, P. A., Hijrah, L., & Nurrohman, R. (2025, August). Beyond The Classroom: How Entrepreneurial Education And Creativity Drive Student Entrepreneurial Interest Through Motivation At Mulawarman University. In *Proceedings International Indonesia Conference On Interdisciplinary Studies (Vol. 1, Pp. 747-759)*.
- Sanistasya, P. A., Hijrah, L., & Nurrohman, R. (2025, August). Beyond The Classroom: How Entrepreneurial Education And Creativity Drive Student Entrepreneurial Interest Through Motivation At Mulawarman University. In *Proceedings International Indonesia Conference On Interdisciplinary Studies (Vol. 1, Pp. 747-759)*.
- Sari, E. T., Divinagracia, M. R. G., & Wardhani, P. S. (2021). Entrepreneurial Project-Based Education Through E-Learning Among Employed College Students. *International Journal Of Innovation And Applied Studies*, 33(3), 1-7.
- Sekarningtyas, H., & Firdaus, M. A. (2025). Peningkatan Kompetensi Kewirausahaan Mahasiswa Melalui Pelatihan Business Model Canvas Dan Strategi Digital Marketing Di Era Mbkm. *Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat Bakti Negeri*, 2(1), 29-37.
- Soraya, D. U., Elmunsyah, H., & Pamungkas, B. D. (2025). Peran Paparan Konten Media Sosial Bermuatan Kewirausahaan Dan Penggunaan Tools Digital Marketing Terhadap Kesiapan Wirausaha Dan Keterampilan Digital Marketing Mahasiswa. *Jipi (Jurnal Ilmiah Penelitian Dan Pembelajaran Informatika)*, 10(2), 1652-1662.
- Soraya, D. U., Elmunsyah, H., & Pamungkas, B. D. (2025). Peran Paparan Konten Media Sosial Bermuatan Kewirausahaan Dan Penggunaan Tools Digital Marketing Terhadap Kesiapan Wirausaha Dan Keterampilan Digital Marketing Mahasiswa. *Jipi (Jurnal Ilmiah Penelitian Dan Pembelajaran Informatika)*, 10(2), 1652-1662.